

If you have a favoured memory or tribute for inclusion in this compilation, please email Howard on hg230@cam.ac.uk

A Gathering of the Raven Clan
a tribute to Professor John Raven
FRS FRSE

Saturday 6th July, 1 - 4 pm

University Botanic Garden
Riverside Drive, Dundee DD2 1QH

Programme:

- 1-2 pm arrival, informal catch ups meet and greet with refreshments
- 2 pm short welcome address by Professor Howard Griffiths
- 2.10 toast to the Raven, tributes and remembrances
- Thereafter, afternoon tea, more drinks, more catching up....
- 4 pm depart

JAR @ CCM9
Cambridge

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Knaresborough 1981
(Nina Griffiths)

- **Howard Griffiths**
- John Raven was an extraordinary character—his breadth of knowledge was unrivalled across the plant sciences. He was an inspirational teacher, and generously supported a legion of postgraduate students and post docs, his ideas providing a platform for their future careers (including my own!).
- Many stories can be told about the seemingly inevitable avalanche of paper across every surface in his office, from which strata a vital document could instantly be recovered; his recall of a specific paper drawn at random from many thousands of diminutive file cards; his pioneering sartorial sense.
- Ultimately, John’s prodigious scientific output represents the mark of a truly original scholar, and his memory will be carried forward by so many of us who were fortunate to have known him

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That Office, with Alessandro Norici and Shona McInroy, Bio Sci
(Alessandro Norici)

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With Alessandro and Shona McInroy, that Office, Bio Sci
Alessandro Norici

John Beardall and Howard Griffiths

-the evenings at 4 Pennan Grove spent listening to vinyl records of Tom Lehrer and Beyond the Fringe... And not only his knowledge of the train timetable, but also every possible aircraft overhead, topped up by his annual pilgrimage to the Leuchars Air Show.

Jane Wishart

- sending post cards from everywhere in the world and answering email questions, usually by return. When I got my job at St Andrews, John sent such a lovely post card which arrived on my desk in my first week. It read “ dear Jane, Sorry you are leaving SCRI, but the St Andrews position seems to be a great opportunity for you – enjoy it! I’ll drop in when I’m in St Andrews”

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CCM1 1984 Asilomar
(Stephen Maberly)

- **Prof Tracy Lawson, University of Essex**
- As current president of the Society of Experimental Biology I would like to acknowledge his contribution to the SEB, not only to science and greatly advancing our understanding of the research topics that span our society, animal, cell and plant but also his contribution to developing the society as an active member

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John has 516 publications in Web of Science (859 in Google Scholar!) covering 10 topic areas from Astrophysics to Plant Sciences to Oceanography

Field	Number of Publications
Plant Sciences	303
Marine Freshwater Biology	95
Ecology	51
Biology	51
Environmental Sciences	17
Ecophysiology	24
Oceanography	25
Environmental Sciences	11
Ecology	12
Evolutionary Molecular Biology	27
Evolutionary Molecular Biology	27
Ecophysiology	24
Ecology	12

(prepared by Stephen Maberly)

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Prof C Barry Osmond Canberra

- For this stumbling antipodean in the Botany School Cambridge UK 1966-67 it was a treat to take a glass of cider with Tom apRees' court in the pub at day's end and there to meet John Raven, then one of Enid MacRobbie's team of astonishingly sharp aspirants in plant biology.
- John and I met often during a later sabbatical in the UK in 1980 when, memorably, he explained that if one hoped to understand boundary-layer effects on $\delta^{13}\text{CO}_2$ fractionation in submerged aquatic plants, more accurate stream water flow rates would be obtained with an orange than with a pooh stick!
- John Raven was the preeminent Polymath of our discipline; plant biology world wide is the poorer today for his passing

2002, Biosphere 2, Arizona (Barry Osmond)

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John published in 64 different journals

Shown here: journals with >1 paper

(prepared by Stephen Maberly)

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Dr Lisa Smolenska (class of 1995)

- He was an amazing man. His lectures are forever imprinted in my mind. A character, a contributor, a brilliant, rare mind and a curator of the most amazing paper "strata" filing system I've ever witnessed.

Karl Abel

- In a lifetime, you do not meet many like John. If you are lucky enough to be taught by him you remember it all your life. If you have the great good fortune to talk with him and work with him then it changes the way you think for the remainder of your life, for the better.

"No, that's not his Freshers Week garb—that's his normal wear."

From the Dundee Courier, 1999, courtesy Ali Roberts

From Prof Kevin Flynn.
 "A fellow FRS, the late Mike Fasham, recounted to me his fears for John's life during a post-workshop visit to a pub in Southampton which was frequented by some drunk dockers. One of the dockers was loud-mouthed comments over John's appearance and staggered over to talk to him. A few minutes later, said docker and John were seen chatting away like long-lost friends....";

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Howard Fallowfield, Flinders University:

- He was a titan, who generously shared ideas and insight with colleagues and students, often spiked with a brilliant sense of humour.

Keith Skene University of Dundee

- An amazing man - so brilliant yet so communicative with a wonderful sense of humour. Who can forget the Rubisco washing powder advert or the black and white acetates of algae that he would place on the glass plate and press copy! He has had such an impact on so many generations of students and we all owe him so much in sharing his unique thinking with us.

Lynn Robertson (now Kerr), class of 1994.

- Prof Raven, unique and special in so many ways but most surely the only man with his own bird nest, in his Uni office, at the top of a pile of newspapers! Thank you for sharing your love of botany and for the fun memories of the BSI.

John at Monikie Silly Hat Party, 1978/9; (Nina Griffiths)

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Professor Willie Wilson, University of Plymouth, and on behalf of the Marine Biological Association, Plymouth

John, you have certainly left a mark on marine biologists worldwide and to the Marine Biological Association MBA specifically; always positive, constructive and insightful with an understanding on pretty much every topic we covered. You were a fabulous mentor to all our Fellows, but most of all we always enjoyed your cheerful company.

Professor David Beerling, University of Sheffield

very sad to hear of John's death, not only a truly brilliant intellect but also a great supporter of younger scientists, including me, back in the day.

Juliet Brodie Natural History Museum

John was a truly remarkable person in so many ways... He was also a highly valued friend and always generous with his time. A great correspondent on a wealth of topics, ask John a scientific question and a stimulating discussion would ensue. And in my office are the many post cards that he sent over the years, a lovely reminder of the care he took to stay in touch.

John and Linda stepping out by the Tay, Inverbay, 1985? (Nina Griffiths)

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Dr Peter von Dassow, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile on behalf of Jane Wong, Osvaldo Ulloa, Juan Diego Gaitan Espitia

We were very happy when John agreed to join our eclectic group of co-authors to analyze a mystery of the disappearance of phytoplankton from where they'd be expected to thrive.

What surprised us was how, whenever the first author Jane sent a new draft, comment, or question, John was always the fastest to respond, always with valuable insight, and suggesting the most relevant papers, whether from the latest literature or from key early work

With Bruce Osborne, Tomar, 2002

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JAR @ CCM9
Cambridge

Prof Steve Long, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign

- John used his encyclopedic knowledge to produce a string of novel insights across plant sciences, yet despite being head and shoulders above the rest of us, was incredibly modest and seemed to always have time for others and give very serious thought and advice on the problems we were tackling, as I first discovered as a first semester graduate student.

Prof Euan Nisbet RHUL

- John was.... one of those rare kind folk who managed to make science fun and to make the world interesting.

Fiona King (undergraduate 1995, Ecology)

- He was the second supervisor for my final year undergraduate research project with Ali Blackwell. This was a duty that he could have taken pretty lightly. Instead he showed a genuine interest in my work, inviting me to come and speak to him about it several times, asking incredibly insightful questions and sharing his views. It was a bit scary being one on one with someone with such a huge brain but he made it easy for me!

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2008 Glen Clova post retirement symposium (Stephen Maberly)

- **Dr Alison Roberts, class of 1994 and JHI colleague**
- John was my professor as an undergraduate and became a friend and mentor. He was the most impressive mind I've ever experienced and I'm so grateful to have known him.
- He was an inspiring and admirable teacher; I'll remember him bouncing between and frantically scribbling on the multiple blackboards in the MSI lecture theatre and enthusiastically leading field trips to hillsides, woods and rocky shores.
- A kind and thoughtful man, always interesting and often amusing company. A formidable scientist. I knew the power of his intellect but he always spoke to me as an equal; powerful indeed! He also taught me that being different is cool, following your heart is valid and living an unusual life can be hugely rewarding.
- Definitely someone to give thanks for, and a life worth celebrating.
- You hugely enriched my life John. Thank you, Allie.

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lhs 1976
Glen Clova
with Ulrich
Luetgge
(Ro Scott)

rhs
Denmark,
1985
(Kath
Richardson)

- **Prof Tracy Lawson, University of Essex**
- One of my first encounters with John Raven was at my PhD board meeting I then asked him a question about a paper I had been reading and something I did not understand - and he said 'ahhhh' - and threw his hand into a pile of papers that was standing floor to ceiling, and like pulling an ace from the pack of cards, he pulled out the paper in question to start explaining it to me.

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Prof Kath Richardson, wedding with Jens, Denmark 1985

- I am sorry that I cannot be with you, but I have had my own quiet little remembrance for John and, in that connection, have found some old pictures that I would like to share with you!
- I hope you all have a good day full of good memories of a wonderful man and friend!

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John as Best Man, F Andrew and Sally Smith's wedding, 1965

- **Prof Andrew (FA) Smith (University of Adelaide)**
- We used to swap sung lines or verses over the low partition between our two desks in small adjoining carrels in the lab., also with benches on which we did short-term experiments with radioisotopes
- Our PhD supervisor Enid MacRobbie usually only expressed displeasure when she was giving small-group tutorials in her lab./office, separated only by a non-soundproof partition. She used to come out, put her hands on her hips and sigh - that signal was enough for us to stop singing.

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Enid MacRobbie, Sally and Andrew Smith, 1965 (Andrew Smith)

- **Prof Dale Sanders University of York**
- John's encyclopaedic knowledge and original thinking was an inspiration to so many plant biologists. A particular landmark for me was his seminal work on control of cytoplasmic pH
- And talking of putting people at ease.. Referring to something that he obviously knew was a mis-print, he said during my viva: "Did you work with a particularly smelly new gas?" "No!???" I was thinking: "what on earth is he talking about?" "Oh, I just wondered about BO2 on page XX - whether this is some new boron compound or something".

We then had a really good laugh, knowing that CO2 was meant. That exchange characterised the rest of the viva: some really very serious and challenging chats about my project interspersed with humour and banter.

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Songs with F Andrew Smith
 Enid was/is proudly Scottish of course... "Miss MacRobbie" because her PhD was not Oxbridge – it was Edinburgh University. Anyway, Enid deserves recognition and thanks for her tolerance.

*Tune: Skye Boat Song.
 ('Bonny Charlie's gone awa'...)*

Miss MacRobbie's gone awa',
 Flying o'er the briny main,
 She's gone to Australia,
 When will she come back again?

When will she come back again?
 When will she come ba-a-ck
 a-a-gai-ain?
 She's gone to Australia,
 When will she come back again?

1979 with Sally and Andrew Smith, Flinders Ranges (Ro Scott)

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Songs with F Andrew Smith

For the IWMTMP meeting at Paris and Rouen, France:
*Tune, Bonny Dundee
 ('To the Lords of Convention 'twas Claverhouse spoke...');*

At the meeting in Rouen t'was Raven who spake,
 All plant cells in general use lots of nitrate,
 But the biggest pH change* that you'll ever see
 Is made by the 'dictyons*' of bonny Dundee.

The fluxes are rapid when energy's high
 and there is an increase in big Delta Psi*
 For the biggest pH change that you'll ever see
 Is made by the 'dictyons' of bonny Dundee.

[*pH change: in external solution due to nitrate uptake, 'dictyons: *Hydrodictyon* (giant-celled alga) on which John worked.]

Another version, for the IWMTMP meeting in Sydney (1986) when John had become interested in photosynthesis:

At the Workshop in Sydney t'was Raven who spake,
 T'is well known that plant cells can carbon uptake.
 But the influxes that you'll ever see,
 Occur when there's influx of HCO three*

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Songs with F Andrew Smith

'Happy Wanderer' Words were composed in a large beer cellar at Jülich, Germany during the International Workshop on Membrane Transport in Plants (IWMTMP) in 1974

Tune: Happy Wanderer, verses 1, 2 and 8.

I love to be a-transported into a living cell,
 For as I go there's counterflow of ions out as well.
 $ZFE = RT \log \text{base } e \text{ of } C_{out} \text{ over } C_{in}$.
 ATP, it drives me, into a living cell.

I love to be accumulated in the vacuole,
 Where all the solutes have a turgor generating role.
 $ZFE = RT \log \text{base } e \text{ of } C_{out} \text{ over } C_{in}$.
 ATP, it drives me, into the vacuole.

I hate to be a-transported into the dictyosome,
 cos when I am in a jam, the cell wall is my home.
 $ZFE = RT \log \text{base } e \text{ of } C_{out} \text{ over } C_{in}$.
 In Golgi, I'm hot free, the cytoplasm to roam.

1979 with Sally and Andrew Smith
 Ro Scott

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Plant Sci Pls 2005
 Claire Halpin

-he was extremely generous and kind to me, showing interest in what I did and always being among the first to send a card of congratulation if I received some accolade. I was in awe of his scientific prowess and impact.. Mike Ferguson, Regius Professor of Life Sciences, University of Dundee

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Life Sciences
 Divn 2007 (Claire H)

- Prof David Read, Sheffield University
- It is hard to contemplate a botanical world-perhaps any world-without him. What a person! Over the years, one of his 'signature' activities involved the sending of post cards-from all corners of the globe-normally from venues of leading international conferences. These were always jovial in spirit-and uplifting in content.

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Sinead Collins, University of Edinburgh

- I miss him. The guy literally phoned Montreal in 2003 when he got my first paper to review, and spent hours on the phone walking me through how a CCM worked. HOURS. ON A PHONE...

Prof Alyson Tobin, Edinburgh Napier University

- I was fortunate enough to teach alongside John on a joint MRes we ran at St Andrews- happy memories of the two of us traipsing around St Andrews with a huddle of students while John talked about N fluxes in and out of the sea and I tried to chip in a few random thoughts while marvelling at his amazing memory for facts and figures

Plant Sciences Xmas party 2015
 (Claire H)

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CCM7 2008 New Orleans
(Stephen Maberly)

Dr. Stephen Maberly CEH Lancaster

- John was an extraordinary scientist and person. He had an exceptional interest, knowledge and insight into a huge range of topics- including some unusual ones such as the wingspan of different types of aircraft! I am very grateful to have been able to work with John: he was a generous collaborator and extremely kind

Dr Ben Long University of Newcastle NSW

- Very sad to hear of John's passing. His contributions to the CCM field are immense.

Dr Jodi Young University of Washington

- John was my external examiner for my DPhil thesis and continued to support me through my career. He was an amazing person and will be sorely missed.

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2008 Glen Clova post retirement symposium
(Stephen Maberly)

Jane Wishart (University of St Andrews)

- ...the first time I met John and Linda – in Glen Prosen around 1985 or 1986. My son, then age 5 or 6 came running in telling me he had found a man, with a big white beard, lying down outside looking at our moss.
- John had time for people - I can only assume he was more or less constantly writing to someone about something and encouraging everyone along the way. I am so very lucky I was able to spend some great times with him and was able to listen to him talk to the students and floor them, of course , with his unbelievable knowledge and his unrivalled wit!

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Raven Retirement Symposium speakers, 2008

Prof Dianne Edwards, University of Cardiff

- Thank you, John-- for the kindly friendship and wisdom that I have been privileged to share over many, many years and for your enormous contributions to our scientific community.

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- Raven Office 1970- 1980 From Linda
- *that cheese, which lived under the glass for more than a decade!

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From Linda:
Field Course Raven

- Steve Hubbard did over 2000h field course teaching with JAR- he did not shirk his teaching duties!
- Bruce Osborne: ... during a field course to Millport with students from Dundee: The local pub had an old style jukebox... when it came to John's turn we were regaled with 'Total Eclipse of the Heart' and 'Lost in France'. Who would have guessed that John was a Bonnie Tyler fan? Of course everyone then played Bonnie Tyler records for the rest of the week!

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That amazing Duncan of Jordanstone Degree ceremony portrait of JAR

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Andrew Smith (JACS), Nina, Howard,
John and Philip White (Linda)

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David Hopkins:
Here's a gentle reflection from John given to an early career academic seeking research grants: "Think about whether you need to write a proposal or just think harder"

Brian Eddy: it was suggested a good way forward would be to seek John's advice. As was often the way, the discussion took place in the main corridor. John quickly identified the main point and went on to expand in depth and in detail on a Zoology topic where I was supposed to be the expert!!!

Katherine Preedy:

My memories of John are of an enveloping warmth, generosity of spirit and personal interest together with a sense of endless possibility. He was a wonderful source of inspiration and advice

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